

SONNETS delivers an innovative methodological framework for public sector organisations and related stakeholders to accelerate the transformation of the public sector through the identification, analysis and take-up of emerging technologies that hold the potential to transform and infuse real value to public services.

OUR VISION

INFORMATION

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SONNETS

SOCIETAL Needs aNalysis and
Emerging Technologies in the public Sector

Transforming the public sector
into a technology and
innovation leader

IDENTIFICATION OF SOCIETAL AND PUBLIC SECTOR NEEDS

INDIVIDUALS

- **Equal employment opportunities**
- **Experiential education and training**
- **Inclusive well-being and health**
- **Transparent and participative access to Public Sector services**
- Connected and integrated Europe
- Environmental Amicability
- Housing and secure shelters
- Modern workplaces
- Prevent rural out-migration
- Need for a democratic access and usability in retail environments
- More effective law enforcement
- Water security
- Fight transnational and organized crime
- More social and infrastructural resilience and better crisis management
- Poverty reduction
- Better alignment between government actions a societal needs
- Promote tolerance and solidarity
- Manage careers evolution in a ageing society

BUSINESS NEEDS

- **Reduce taxation levels and lessen complexity**
- **Easy access to Public Sector information (open data)**
- **Stimulate an entrepreneurial and start-up culture**
- **Streamlined and reliable administrative procedures in the Public Sector**
- Technology implementation
- Business expansion
- Access to a unified European market
- Talent acquisitions and retention
- **Agile and participative Public Sector**
- **Ease of doing business**
- Diffusion of ecodesign and circular value chains
- Promote social responsibility among for profit ventures
- Reduce reskilling time and costs
- Reduce weight of finance on overall overall economy
- Fight tax evasion to promote fairer competition
- Higher coordination with public sector where relevant
- Need for high speed broadband connections outside metropolitan areas

GOVERNMENT NEEDS

- **Appropriate remuneration and incentives**
- **Digitization**
- **Resource optimization**
- **Lean bureaucracy**
- Accessible Public Sector information
- Civil servants as a community of change
- Employee empowerment and recognition
- Rework the trust deficit
- Participative democracy
- **Recruitment, training (and IT Literacy)**
- Exploring quasi-market solutions for public service delivery
- Leverage crowdsourcing
- Limit impact of the spoil system
- Assign political roles to people with specific expertise in the relevant domain
- Reduce use of jargon for improved communication effectiveness towards stakeholders
- Promote inter-agency collaboration
- Improving risk management and resilience
- Promote teleworking

Legend

1. Long list of needs form desk research (53 pink + grey)
2. Preliminary short list of needs from privileged informants (28 pink)
3. Final short list of needs from online and offline validation activities (12 pink bold).

For further information:

<http://www.sonnets-project.eu/content/results>

